

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Elida, T., Rahardjo, W., & Raharjo, A. (2024). Impulse Buying: How Generation Z's Enjoyment of Shopping Affects Their Fashion Buys. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 7(2), 96-107.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.07.02.579

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Impulse Buying: How Generation Z's Enjoyment of Shopping Affects Their Fashion Buys

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Abstract

This study examined the determinants that impact Generation Z's impulsive purchasing of fashion products. Implementing Stimulus Organism Responses (SOR), the research model is structured as Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). External stimuli include Price Discounts and Store Environment, with Shopping Enjoyment mediating between Hedonic Shopping Motivation and these two factors. In total, 444 students between the ages of 18 and 22 participated. Form questionnaires were distributed to 30 WhatsApp group classes to collect the data. Hedonic shopping motivation, price discount, and store environment contribute to an enjoyable shopping experience, stimulating impulsive purchasing. The determinant influencing impulsive purchasing is the store atmosphere. Impulse buying behavior is carried out using the stimulus organism response (SOR) theory approach. One of the stimuli used in the research model, the online store atmosphere, is still not widely studied.

Keywords: Consumer Behavior, Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Impulse Buying, Online Shopping, Price Discount, Shopping Enjoyment, Store Atmosphere Online

1. Introduction

Impulse buying behavior has been a phenomenon that has attracted attention in consumer behavior research over the past decades (Shen and Khalifa, 2012; Mohan, Sivakumaran and Sharma, 2013; Peng and Kim, 2014; Atulkar and Kesari, 2018; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Lee and Chen, 2021; Aiolfi, Bellini and Grandi, 2022; Kumagai and Nagasawa, 2022; Lin et al., 2022; Sun, Li and Sun, 2023). The impulse buying phenomenon is mainly due to lifestyle changes and technological developments affecting people's shopping. Generation Z is influenced by impulse buying behavior (Djafarova and Bowes, 2021; Munsch, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). They are a generation born and raised in the digital era, often called digital natives.

The materialistic nature of Generation Z (Flurry and Swimberghe, 2016), sensitivity to trends and lifestyles, and constant desire to appear fashionable motivate this demographic to purchase items that express their individuality (Djafarova and Bowes, 2021). Muhammad et al. (2023) found that Generation Z is susceptible to the positive stimuli that fashion products frequently provide; these stimuli are commonly linked to trends and social, environmental, and multicultural concerns (Johnson and Im, 2014; Razzaq et al., 2018; Slater and Demangeot, 2021) elicitation of positive emotions in response to a positive stimulus induces impulsive purchasing (Gupta and Gentry, 2018; Muhammad, Adeshola and Isiaku, 2023). Therefore, Generation Z is a consumer group susceptible to impulsive purchasing (Djafarova and Bowes, 2021; Munsch, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021).

Conversely, impulse buying demonstrates the seller's proficiency in executing his sales strategy (Aiolfi, Bellini and Grandi, 2022). Research on impulse buying is crucial for businesses to comprehend consumer behavior and ensure their continued existence. The fashion industry is currently marked by intense competition, as evidenced by the proliferation of online retailers carrying a wide range of brands. The fashion industry may have a market expansion opportunity with the 41 percent share of Generation Z. In addition, numerous studies have demonstrated that Generation Z actively purchases and consumes goods from a variety of online marketplaces; thus, it is considered one of the most influential consumer groups (Nghia, Olsen and Trang, 2020; Azhar et al., 2023; Van den Bergh, De Pelsmacker and Worsley, 2023).

Several scholarly investigations have been undertaken to examine the purchasing patterns of Generation Z through the lens of generational cohort theory, which emphasizes the characteristics of cohorts (Ismail et al., 2020; Agrawal, 2022; Thangavel, Pathak and Chandra, 2022; Van den Bergh, De Pelsmacker and Worsley, 2023). Another approach used is the Theory of Planned Behavior (Djafarova and Fouts, 2022; Pradeep and Pradeep, 2023; Suzianti, Amaradhanny and Fathia, 2023); the theory of Acceptance Model (Lestari, 2019), which uses the gratification theory (Siregar et al., 2023), and social commerce adoption model that focuses on specific platforms (Azhar et al., 2023). An additional study employs Stimulus Organism Response (SOR) Theory to comprehend the purchasing patterns of Generation Z as deviant behavior from a clinical standpoint ((Mason et al., 2022).

Regarding the impulse purchasing behavior of Generation Z, Abdelsalam et al. (2020) suggest in a meta-analysis that four factors warrant investigation: site performance, marketing strategies, consumer characteristics, and social factors. Redline et al. (2023) propose a similar notion, stating that the antecedent variables of impulse purchasing behavior consist of sociodemographic factors, marketing mix, store-related factors, online peer influence, and consumer-related factors. These studies prove that external and internal elements can influence impulse purchasing behavior. External factors include marketing strategies and shopping environments, while internal factors involve consumer characteristics. Within online shopping, the subsequent stimuli will foster impulsive buying behavior (Chan, Cheung and Lee, 2017). Subsequently, the Stimulus Organism Response (SOR) model offers a coherent framework for the assessment of the model within the scope of this investigation (Lee & Chen, 2021; Shetu, 2023; Zafar et al., 2021, 2023).

This study examined the determinants that impact Generation Z's impulsive purchases of fashion products. This behavior is a compelling subject of investigation due to its potential to inform marketers, among others, in creating consumer-centric marketing strategies that effectively target Generation Z as a prospective market.

1.1. Conceptual Framework And Hypotheses

1.1.1. Impulse Buying

Impulsive buying is a consumer's irrational behavior (Wells, Parboteeah and Valacich, 2011; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020). Several variables, including the shopping environment (Mohan, Sivakumaran and Sharma, 2013; Atulkar and Kesari, 2018; Geng et al., 2020; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Xiao et al., 2022), hedon behavior (Peng and Kim, 2014; Lee and Wu, 2017; Vieira, Santini and Araujo, 2018; Çavuşoğlu, Demirağ and Durmaz, 2020; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Park and Lin, 2020; Kumagai and Nagasawa, 2022; Lin et al., 2022; Sun, Li and Sun, 2023) are hypotheses that influence impulse buying. Previous research has established a correlation between impulsive buying and marketing tactics, including the implementation of discounted pricing (Sheehan et

al., 2019; Büyükdağ, Soysal and Kitapci, 2020; Çavuşoğlu, Demirağ and Durmaz, 2020). In addition, an enjoyable experience on one of the e-commerce platforms may stimulate impulsive purchases (Atulkar and Kesari, 2018; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Lee and Chen, 2021; Lin et al., 2022).

1.1.2. Stimulus Organism Response (SOR)

Stimulus-organism response (SOR) Theory is a conceptual framework utilized to elucidate the mechanisms by which organisms react to stimuli, subsequently generating distinct behavioral responses ((Russell and Mehrabian, 1974). Within the marketing realm, this stimulus will increase consumers' propensity to categorize, interact with, and identify pages and their desire to revisit the page to purchase products or conversely (De Luca and Botelho, 2021). Product categories, pricing, discounts, brand advocates, and website functionalities are examples of marketing, social, and technological strategies that constitute external stimuli on e-commerce platforms (Chan, Cheung and Lee, 2017; Büyükdağ, Soysal and Kitapci, 2020; Zafar et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2022) The stimulus may also manifest as an intrinsic internal factor that is personal, as exemplified by the characteristics of the hedon (Peng and Kim, 2014; Lee and Wu, 2017; Vieira, Santini and Araujo, 2018; Çavuşoğlu, Demirağ and Durmaz, 2020; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Park and Lin, 2020).

The term "organism" in the SOR model refers to the individual or person who responds to the stimulus (Russell and Mehrabian, 1974). The organism is an active and mediating factor that processes the stimulus and generates a response based on internal feelings or behavior (Russell and Mehrabian, 1974; Shen and Khalifa, 2012; Richard and Chebat, 2016; Chen et al., 2019; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020). The organism plays a crucial role in shaping the response to a stimulus, and various factors, such as emotions and cognitive processes, can influence the answer. Internal processes in the organism can be both affective and cognitive. The existing literature highlights that emotions play a central role during impulse purchases compared to cognition (Floh and Madlberger, 2013). Therefore, this study highlights the affective process of the stimulus that will elicit a sense of pleasure as an emotional reaction during impulse purchases (Chan, Cheung and Lee, 2017; Li, Wang and Cao, 2022).

Consumer response, as defined by De Luca and Botelho (2021), can manifest as either approach or avoidance behavior. In the context of this research, response was utilized as a surrogate for impulsive purchases (see also Zafar et al., 2021). A consumer adheres to the behavioral approach by conducting a product search on the webpage, culminating in completing the purchase process. Behavior that avoids is the antithesis.

1.1.3. Hedonic Shopping Motivation

Hedonic Shopping Motivation is a person's drive or motivation to shop because they seek pleasure, personal satisfaction, or positive experiences gained from shopping (Peng and Kim, 2014; Vieira, Santini and Araujo, 2018; Iyer et al., 2019; Çavuşoğlu, Demirağ and Durmaz, 2020; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Kumagai and Nagasawa, 2022) Several studies show that hedon properties are one of the internal factors that drive impulse buying (Peng and Kim, 2014; Lee and Wu, 2017; Vieira, Santini and Araujo, 2018; Çavuşoğlu, Demirağ and Durmaz, 2020; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Park and Lin, 2020) When someone has a solid hedonic motivation to shop, they tend to experience higher levels of satisfaction during the shopping process (Vieira, Santini and Araujo, 2018; Kumagai and Nagasawa, 2022) The level of satisfaction will provide a positive and pleasant experience in shopping. Based on this, the first hypothesis that can be made is that *hedonic shopping motivation is predicted to increase shopping enjoyment*.

1.1.4. Price Discount

Price is commonly regarded as a determinant of purchasing choices (Sheehan et al., 2019; Büyükdağ, Soysal and Kitapci, 2020; Çavuşoğlu, Demirağ and Durmaz, 2020). Sellers may employ a discount price strategy to stimulate impulse buying (Lee & Chen, 2021; Lin et al., 2022; Peng & Kim, 2014). The magnitude of the discount affects purchase intentions dynamically over an online shopping experience, indicating that consumers enjoy the process of finding and using discounts (Sheehan et al., 2019). In online shopping, consumers always look for the best deals, as the price is an attractive stimulant in this environment (Atulkar and Kesari, 2018; Aiolfi, Bellini and

Grandi, 2022). Discounts can be considered an incentive to get people to shop, making shopping more enjoyable and satisfying (Lee & Chen-Yu, 2018). Discounts can enhance the emotional experience of online shopping, stimulate purchase intentions, and increase the enjoyment of the shopping process (Huo et al., 2023; Lee & Chen-Yu, 2018; Venkatesh et al., 2021). As a result, the second hypothesis that can be formulated based on the findings of this study is that *price discounts are predicted to increase shopping enjoyment*.

1.1.5. Store Atmosphere

A store atmosphere is an environment that is intentionally crafted to impact the mood and conduct of customers (Ahmed and Ting, 2020; Albarq, 2021; Calvo-Porrall and Lévy-Mangin, 2021; Xiao et al., 2022). Aspects of an online store's ambiance consist of page layout, navigation, colors, fonts, images, and videos (Zhao et al., 2022). These characteristics are expected to create a positive shopping experience that encourages customers to surf, shop, and buy products (Lin et al., 2022). The level of interactivity and information technology (IIT) of an online store can affect consumer perception of the online retail environment, shopping enjoyment, and patronage behavior towards online retailers (Kim, Fiore and Lee, 2007). So if during surfing consumers feel a positive experience, then a sense of pleasure will arise during shopping. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that *the quality of the store atmosphere is predicted to increase shopping enjoyment*.

1.1.6. Shopping Enjoyment

Shopping enjoyment pertains to the degree of gratification or pleasure an individual experiences while engaging in the activity of shopping (Kim, Fiore and Lee, 2007; Floh and Madlberger, 2013; Mohan, Sivakumaran and Sharma, 2013; Badgaiyan and Verma, 2014; Atulkar and Kesari, 2018; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020). Based on previous research, it is said that hedonic shopping motivation, price discounts, and store atmosphere are predicted to increase shopping enjoyment. Experiencing pleasure while shopping manifests positive emotions that impair rationality, judgment, and self-control, compelling consumers to engage in excessive shopping (Becker & Bernecker, 2023; Lee, Gan, & Liew, 2023). Experiencing this degree of delight in shopping may inspire impulse buying (Horváth and Adıgüzel, 2018a; Hashmi, Shu and Haider, 2020; Aiolfi, Bellini and Grandi, 2022). As illustrated in Figure 1, further hypothetical is postulated that *hedonic shopping motivation, price discounts, and store atmosphere are predicted to increase impulse buying through shopping enjoyment*.

Figure 1: Model Hypothesis

This model includes gender as a control variable, related to research results that show the influence of gender on impulse buying behavior (Atulkar and Kesari, 2018; Bhatia, 2019; Djafarova and Bowes, 2021). Although different things are shown by Büyükdağ et al. (2020), conclude that impulse purchasing behavior does not differ by gender. Gender was incorporated as a control variable in this research, taking into account the general tendency for women to be more susceptible to the influence of fashion products.

2. Method

Research variables, namely Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Price Discount, Store Atmosphere Shopping Enjoyment, and Impulse Buying are latent variables developed based on previous research as listed in the

Appendix Table. Each variable is measured using five constructs. The construct on each latent variable was measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = "strongly disagree"; 5 = "strongly agree"). Before data collection, face validity is performed on the questionnaire, and a test of the validity and reliability of the construct is carried out. The items of each variable after the validity and reliability tests are expressed in Table 1.

The respondents of this study were students aged 18 to 22 years. Data was collected using a questionnaire in the form of a Google form distributed to 30 WhatsApp group classes at a university in West Java. The respondents of this study are Generation Z, who have purchased fashion products on the e-commerce platform and Instagram social media. Data collection was carried out from August to December 2022. Referring to the research model (Figure 1), the minimum sample size that must be taken is ten times the number of constructs in each variable, which is 250 (Hair et al., 2017). The number of respondents in this study was 444 people. This research model was analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The utilized application is Smart PLS 3.0.

The assessments of the items' reliability and validity are presented in Table 1. All variables have Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values that exceed 0.5. The values of Cronbach's Alpha, Rho A, and Composite Reliability exceed 0.7. According to Hair et al. (2017), it can be concluded that the utilized construct is reliable and valid.

Table 1: Validity and Reliability Test

Variables	Reliability			Validity
	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Hedonic Shopping Motivation	0.898	0.902	0.925	0.713
Price Discount	0.880	0.883	0.913	0.678
Store Atmosphere	0.848	0.852	0.892	0.623
Shopping Enjoyment	0.850	0.851	0.893	0.626
Impulse Buying	0.834	0.838	0.883	0.601

Tests for model fit are detailed in Table 2. The fact that the Standardized Root Mean Square (SRMR) is below 0.08 indicates that this model is compatible with the data. The appropriateness of this model is further validated by the loading factor values, all exceeding 0.7 (Appendix Table). Three exogenous variables can accurately predict shopping enjoyment, as the R² value of 0.862 indicated. A moderate correlation is observed between impulsive purchasing and shopping enjoyment, with a value of 0.435. Q² is an additional fit model parameter that indicates the precision of the research model's predictions. The moderate Q² value is 0.511. Thus, concerning Hair et al. (2019), this model can be utilized to elucidate Generation Z's impulse buying behavior.

Table 2: Model Fit

	Value
SRMR	0,063
R ² Shopping Enjoyment	0,827
R ² Impulse Buying	0,437
Q ²	0.511

3. Results

As shown in Table 3, fashion purchases are conducted via e-commerce platforms and Instagram. Instagram and Shopee are two of the most popular e-commerce platforms for fashion purchases. When examined concerning the gender composition of specific e-commerce platforms, the inclinations of males and females concerning fashion retailers are virtually indistinguishable.

Table 3: Distribution of Fashion Purchases by Gender in Online Stores

Online Shop	Shopee	Lazada	Instagram	Tokopedia	Zalora	Total
Female	23,20	3,38	24,10	2,70	1,13	54,50
Male	20,04	2,70	19,82	2,03	0,90	45,50
Total	43,24	6,08	43,92	4,73	2,03	100,00

The statistical analysis presented in Table 4 indicates that the variables of hedonic shopping motivation, price discount, and store atmosphere significantly influence shopping enjoyment, as noted in a p-value less than 0.05. The correlation between shopping enjoyment and impulsive purchasing also exhibits a substantial influence value. Additionally, the statistical analysis displayed in Table 4 suggests that gender does not substantially impact impulse buying.

Table 4: Path Coefficient

	Coefficient	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Hedonic Shopping Motivation -> Shopping Enjoyment	0.162	0.051	3.169	0.002
Price Discount -> Shopping Enjoyment	0.360	0.053	6.786	0.000
Store Atmosphere -> Shopping Enjoyment	0.429	0.065	6.629	0.000
Shopping Enjoyment -> Impulse Buying	0.664	0.041	16.269	0.000
Gender (Var Control) -> Impulse Buying	0.042	0.033	1.248	0.213

The indirect effect value of the three exogenous variables on impulse purchases via shopping enjoyment is presented in Table 5. The observed magnitude indicates that Store Atmosphere exerts a more significant influence than the other two variables.

Table 5: Indirect Effect

	Indirect Effect
Hedonic Shopping Motivation -> Shopping Enjoyment-> Impulse Buying	0.108
Price Discount -> Shopping Enjoyment-> Impulse Buying	0.239
Store Atmosphere -> Shopping Enjoyment -> Impulse Buying	0.285

4. Discussion

According to research findings, hedonic shopping motivation significantly impacts shopping enjoyment among Generation Z. This provides further evidence in favor of the proposition that individuals belonging to Generation Z engage in purchasing activities to attain immediate gratification (Djafarova and Bowes, 2021; Munsch, 2021). Generation Z is frequently emotionally invested in the fashion industry due to its propensity to monitor trends and endorse aesthetics. Hedonic motivation can obscure self-control, incite curiosity, and intensify the desire for pleasure in purchasing goods (Chang et al., 2023). When individuals with high hedonic shopping motivation seek emotional satisfaction from their purchases, they are likelier to experience shopping pleasure (Kim et al., 2021). The discovery of a fashionable item one adores will lead to an enhanced shopping experience. Hence, it is probable that Generation Z will derive greater pleasure from the act of shopping when their hedonic desires can be satisfied (Horváth and Adıgüzel, 2018b; Ong et al., 2022).

The impact of price discounts on the enjoyment of shopping is substantial. Generation Z, primarily students in this study, has a limited budget, so they are susceptible to price reductions. They perceive discounts as an immediate incentive to buy fashion (Kim et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2018). They are content due to the perception that the difference in purchase price has resulted in cost savings (Flavian, Guinaliu and Lu, 2020; Mayhoub and Rabboh, 2022). Price reductions are also regarded as amusing and playful by consumers driven by hedonic motivation (Kwok and Uncles, 2005). This will frequently override the necessity of the product and further incentivize a customer to make a purchase (Venkatesh et al., 2021).

The results of statistical tests show that store atmosphere significantly affects shopping enjoyment (Table 4). Consumers who seek emotional satisfaction in shopping tend to feel greater satisfaction when shopping in an attractive store environment. Practical product layout and placement can stimulate consumers to browse more products (Shoenberger and Kim, 2019; Sharma and Bumb, 2022). In addition, visual displays in online stores increase the sensation of shopping (Krasnikolakis et al., 2018). On Shopee and Instagram, vendors frequently carry out visual displays like live sales. This particular aspect is what attracts a more significant number of participants to this online store. Live online sales often employ the participation of significant others, such as well-known individuals or sellers affiliated with the store in question. This practice aims to create a positive impression and foster a relaxed atmosphere through direct reciprocal exchanges, which may potentially sway customers towards impulsive purchasing decisions (Kim et al., 2021; Li, Wang and Cao, 2022; Lin et al., 2022).

This study's results align with Lee & Chen (2021), who show that consumers tend to impulse buy if they feel happy when interacting with the shopping environment. Generation Z, who grew up with technology and social media, the shopping experience is often associated with entertainment and self-expression. When Generation Z enjoys shopping and feels good, they tend to be more prone to impulse purchases. In addition, the influence of social media content, such as reviews, photos, and videos, can increase shopping enjoyment and trigger impulse buying.

As shown in Table 5, the influence of store atmosphere on impulse buying is more dominant than hedonic motivation and price discounts. This shows that Generation Z still considers what is presented in the store, such as clear product information, display, and accurate navigation, so it is possible to surf precisely and efficiently. The accuracy of product information, clear product display, and easy navigation reflects the quality of the online store (Barnes and Vidgen, 2006). Thus, generation Z does not solely satisfy their hedonic motivations or are tempted by discounts in online shopping; they also consider the store's quality. This shows that Generation Z is a wise buyer.

Gender-related research findings show a non-significant effect on impulse buying. These results are in line with the findings of Büyükdag et al. (2020). In contrast, Djafarova & Bowes (2021) show that the behavior of men and women differs in buying products on Instagram, where women are more easily influenced than men. This is allegedly related to the findings of this study, which shows Generation Z is more concerned about the quality of stores than satisfying their hedonic motivations. In addition, adolescent male and female consumers have equal levels of hedonic motivation. Still, men find it easier to buy products with consideration of choice and clarity of product information without taking into account other people's opinions or cost savings (Sramova and Pavelka, 2019).

5. Conclusion and Implication

The findings of this study show that Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Price Discounts, and Store Atmosphere can predict impulse buying behavior through Shopping Enjoyment. Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Price Discounts, and Store Atmosphere stimulate the excitement of shopping and further encourage impulse buying. Impulse buying behavior in fashion products does not differ between men and women.

Store atmosphere affects impulse buying more than the other two variables. This finding is essential for marketers to maintain their online store environment so that consumers feel comfortable, including easy page navigation, accurate information, and quality image display. Meanwhile, hedonic motivation is the weakest antecedent in influencing impulse buying. This is an illustration that strengthens the fact that the most significant factor for students to do impulse buying is not hedonic motivation, which may be influenced by income or the amount of money they have.

Another thing that can be input for business people is setting the right price promotion strategy. Flash sales on specific dates will encourage impulse buying because consumers are limited to a narrow time, so they cannot consider well whether the product offered is what is needed. On the other hand, business people are still responsible

for educating their consumers to be wise in buying products. One form of education that can be provided is, for example, providing honest and accurate information about a product.

This research has not specifically determined the products that are the object of impulse buying carried out by participants. This may show different results from previous studies, where gender did not significantly influence impulse buying. This point is important to note, considering that in online purchases, (1) the object of purchase that is the favorite of men and women is usually different in general ((Pascual-Miguel, Agudo-Peregrina and Chaparro-Peláez, 2015) et al., 2015), (2) women are more easily influenced by peers in buying online products (Garbarino and Strahilevitz, 2004) (3) men and women have quite different perceptions in the process of deepening the introduction of product details (Lin et al., 2019; Yi, 2022).

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

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